

A simple hydrographic survey shows: Rosdorfer Baggersee is much shallower as claimed in the public

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Abstract

Determining the depth of artificial ponds and natural lakes is crucial to know how deep such water bodies are. Surprisingly little is known, however, even about the depths of well-frequented waters from which one would normally expect a wealth of well-documented scientific information. One such case is the Rosdorfer Baggersee near Göttingen (Lower Saxony, Germany). To change that, the authors founded the hydrographic survey "Seevermessung Rosdorf" ("SeVeRo"). Within the frame of this survey, we measured the depth of the Rosdorfer Baggersee using a handheld echo sounder at ~1700 spatially distributed positions, covering the entire extent of the pond. We then developed a bathymetric map by interpolating measured pond depth on a 2 x 2 m grid based on a kriging approach. The main objectives of the study were

- 1) to determine how deep the quarry pond is in order to know how deep it is (greatest depth), and
- 2) to check if commonly reported depths correspond to the actual greatest depth of the quarry pond.

We found that the deepest point of the pond is much shallower (~23 m) than generally claimed by local media and Wikipedia (30-60 m). Commonly reported information about the depth of the Rosdorfer Baggersee and conclusions drawn from this information should hence be reconsidered. Our measurements further show that the pond's shores are characterized by steep edges especially in the northern part, with few locations having slopes up to 70° (~3 m depth at 1 m distance from the shore). Such steep edges should be treated with caution when using the pond for recreational purposes, such as cooling down feet during hiking trips at hot summer days, dog walking, or illegal activities such as swimming and bathing in the pond. Readers should note that the slope map presented here only has a maximum of ~ 23° and therefore underestimates such extraordinary drops. But it might still be a valuable addition to the bathymetric map to find low risk areas for activities at the pond's shores.

Our results provide a baseline to inform the interested public about actual depth of the the Rosdorfer Baggersee and areas with dangerously steep slopes.

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Introduction

For many years, the authors have been wondering about the depth of the Rosdorfer Baggersee, a quarry pond near Göttingen (Lower Saxony, Germany) which is very popular among the local population as a recreational area. People often cool down feet during hiking trips at hot summer days, walk their dogs or enjoy soaking, swimming, dipping, snorkeling, diving, splashing and boating.

But the quarry pond has always caused a stir in Göttingen, especially because of the frequent fatalities that occurred here during the last years. Besides suicide, homicide, and heat stroke, drowning is the most common cause of death at the quarry pond (Wikipedia, 2022). The supposedly very great depth of the quarry pond is always popularly construed to mean that the quarry pond is particularly dangerous for swimmers. In the local press, therefore, practically every time a person drowns in the quarry pond, it is claimed that it would be dangerously deep, just as if one could not drown in much shallower waters. This may distract from other hazards at quarry ponds, such as loose sediments close to steep slopes that can easily break off and pull down even experienced swimmers. The sole leader in dramatically exaggerated pond depths is daily newspaper for the area of Northern Hesse and Southern Lower Saxony, which stated that the pond is a maximum of 60 m deep (HNA, 2015). The same newspaper later claims that it is indeed a bit shallower (without stating why they think so now), but still at least 40 m deep (HNA, 2022). Similar figures are presented by other sources (e.g. HarzKurier 2022). Some more cautious authors used to claim that the pond was only up to 30 m deep (GT, 2015), but finally do not want to be left behind in the race for big numbers and now report depths > 40 m (GT, 2022). However, the only non-newspaper source the authors found for depth of the pond was an article on Wikipedia. It states that the Rosdorfer Baggersee has a maximum depth of 43 m (Wikipedia, 2022). So far, a systematic assessment of the ponds depth and its spatial variability is lacking, which may be used to inform the general public based on scientific evidence. We think that all the commonly reported depths are heavily exaggerated to catch the attention of readers but of course we had no evidence for this claim.

Therefore, the authors decided to start the hydrographic survey "SeVeRo" (Seevermessung Rosdorf; Rosdorf Quarry Pond Survey) to solve the mystery of the true depth of the Rosdorfer Baggersee. To this end, the authors organized two boats, an echo sounder, a handheld GPS device, and cheap and willing labor force to find the deepest point of the quarry pond. From the sampling points, a bathymetric map of the pond was created during our work, which we present here. Based on this map, a slope map was created to better identify very steep areas.

Material and Methods

The Rosdorfer Baggersee is located about 3 km south of Göttingen and 500 m southeast of Rosdorf in direct proximity to the river Leine to the west which appears as a line of trees in Google Earth images (Figure 1). The pond extends about 750 m in a north-south direction and at its widest distance about 250 m in an east-west direction. It has been formed since the 1960s by gravel mining (Wikipedia, 2022). In the northern part, gravel excavation is still in progress. It is conducted with a floating dredger attached to swimming conveyor belts looking like a string of pearls on Google Earth images (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Google Earth image of the Rosdorfer Baggersee ©Google Earth 2022.

The conveyer belts are attached to what we call “the peninsula of gravel wash” (PeGraWa), a penis-shaped piece of land extending into the quarry pond. The northern testicle of PeGraWa is mainly used for landing freshly excavated gravel and transferring it eastward away from the quarry pond. The southern testicle indicates locations where we think sediments from gravel processing have been back-washed into the pond in former years. At the small brownish extension of the southern testicle, sediments are currently being transported to the pond. This area is the part of the shoreline that is changing the fastest due to sedimentation.

Between June and July 2022 the hydrographic survey started with several different expeditions on and around the Rosdorfer Baggersee. Two inflatable boats connected by a 2 m rope were used to conduct four expedition tours on the pond, each on sunny, unclouded days. No significant changes in quarry pond water levels were evident between the tours. An echo sounder (Plastimo Echotest II) and a GPS (GARMIN GPSMAP 65st) were used to determine water depth and geographic position. The first and second expedition tours took the measurement team closely along the quarry ponds shore; the third crisscrossed the quarry pond. The fourth tour explored areas, where we felt that the kriging variance

of an initial version of the bathymetric map derived from the data of the first three missions was still too high.

Since entering, swimming, and boating on the quarry pond is prohibited, we do not provide details about the identities of the persons involved in data collection. The authors of the study deny to have conducted any navigation on the quarry pond or walking on its shores and surroundings. Only this much can be said: An anonymous person in the rear boat was constantly measuring the depth of the water with the echo sounder and was performing a position fix with the GPS. The number of each GPS coordinate pair recorded and the corresponding water depth were transmitted to the boat in front by simply shouting loudly. In the front boat, the data were then received by means of the ears of a second anonymous person and noted with a ballpoint pen (Schneider 132503 Slider Rave XB) in a writing pad (Collegelock Brunnen A5 160 sheets in square). Two other people in the front boat took over rowing and steering the pair of boats. In addition to the echo sounder measurements, one reference measurement was made at the deepest point of the quarry pond with a tape measure (RICHTER Rahmen Stahlmaßband Metri 50 m weißlackiert Anfang B Genauigkeit II) to re-check the echo sounder. The end of the tape measure was tied to a brick (Unipor Mauerziegel Kleinformat NF 24 cm x 11.5 cm x 7.1 cm), which was thrown into the water while an anonymous person held the remaining part of the tape measure in its hands. No significant discrepancies were found between the two systems.

Furthermore, an expedition on foot along the shoreline of the pond was conducted. During this walk, another anonymous person took GPS measurements while holding one foot in the water and one foot on land during the recordings. All water depths of this expedition on foot along the shoreline were set to 0 m thereafter. After these expeditions, the data were read out from the GPS and the water depths recorded during the boat expeditions were added by hand. A variogram model was automatically fitted to the compiled dataset and a map with a 2 m grid resolution was generated by ordinary kriging with R package automap (Hiemstra, 2022). A spatial polygon was created from the data points gathered during the expedition on foot and buffered 2 m out. The maps resulting from the kriging procedure were then masked with this polygon to exclude areas that were clearly on land. In choosing the grid size we followed the advice of Tomislav Hengl: "No absolute ideal pixel size exists, that is for sure" (Hengl 2006, p.1297). We simply felt that 2 m was good enough to provide an overview on water depth to interested readers on a map. Further, a 10-fold cross validation was conducted to assess interpolation quality. All depth values in the text are given as absolute (positive) numbers (e.g., 10 m) to conform to the number formats used by other authors. All depth values in the figures are given as negative values (meters below the water surface) because otherwise negative axis labels for values on land would result, which would be less intuitive for readers. All data analysis was conducted using R version 4.2.0 (R Core Team, 2022).

Results and Discussion

In total 1713 points have been sampled to create the map (Figure 2). The points are colored based on their latitude in order to assist the interpretation of the results of the 10-fold cross validation shown in Figure 4).

Figure 2: Sampling locations of the four boat expeditions and the expedition by foot on and around the Rosdorfer Baggersee in the framework of SeVeRo. The points are colored based on their latitude (i.e. north = blue, south = red).

R package automap produced a gaussian variogram with small nugget effect and a range of 84 m (Figure 3). Playing around with greater range or higher sill via R package gstat (Pebesma und Graeler, 2022) did not lead to much different maps. This is due to the fact, that ordinary kriging results depend mostly on the variogram values at the smallest distances, where variances are small denoting to highest correlations (whuber, 2015).

Figure 3: Variogram produced by R package automap.

Changing the nugget had pronounced effects, especially on the derived slope maps and is discussed below. The 10-fold cross-validation showed – besides few pronounced outliers – good agreement between modelled and measured depths (Figure 4). It appears that residuals at shallower depths (0 to 10 m) are in general somewhat larger compared to deeper points. This might be due to the rapid changes in quarry pond depth near the shores, which are hard to predict while the pond bottom has usually more gentle slopes.

Figure 4: Measured depths of the Rosdorfer Baggersee (m) compared to modelled depths (m) resulting from a 10-fold cross-validation (ME= mean error, MAE = mean absolute error, RMSE = root mean squared error, PBIAS = percent bias, R² = coefficient of determination, n = number of observations, 1:1 line). Depths below the water surface are given as negative values. The points are colored based on their latitude (i.e. north = blue, south = red).

Apparently, deviations at shallower depths are usually higher in the waters of the north (blue circles) compared to the south (red circles), i.e. blue circles are mostly further apart from the 1:1 line compared to red ones. In the north where gravel excavation is still in progress, the lake bottom is rather rough and bumpy and the edges are very steep. The model clearly underperforms in predicting such rapid changes in the ponds underwater topography. Its performance seems to be better in the southern part, where sudden drops have already leveled off during decades of underwater landscape evolution.

Obviously, the model has problems in predicting the exact location of the shore (0 m water depth), as indicated by a large scatter in the data at a measured depth of 0 m. This problem occurs because depth values "on land" (i.e., values above the water level) are not available at the edge of the kriging area. A future approach should therefore convert the depth values of the pond to heights above sea level and add more "on land" data to create an elevation model of the lake bottom together with the adjacent shores. This would increase kriging accuracy on the shores and also allow e.g. for the prediction of shorelines at variable water depths.

The deepest location of the quarry pond is just south of the PeGraWa penis, the narrowest location of the quarry pond. It measures ~ 23 m (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Bathymetric map of the Rosdorfer Baggersee. Depths below the water surface are given as negative values.

To the east of the deepest part of the Rosdorfer Baggersee the previously described southern testicle of PeGraWa is located where the sediments of the gravel washing have been or are still being discharged (Figure 5). Here even something like a wide bathing beach of fine material has developed. It may well be that the quarry pond was originally deeper than 23 m closed to this area, and has only flattened due to years of sediment input. Of course, this requires massive amounts of sediments. Since

we cannot estimate the sediment yield during excavation and processing of gravel now, this can only remain a speculation of scientists who need to fill the discussion part of their paper. But given the unchecked retelling of tall tales by the local press and the source less claims of few Wikipedia authors, this interpretation of the facts might certainly be a very attractive way to save face for them. However, we would like to warn against using this hazarded speculation once again as a fixed truth, because in a few years we might feel like collecting historical facts about gravel mining at Rosdorfer Baggersee and using a landscape evolution model (e.g. Bock et al., 2018) to analyze the possibility of such sedimentation patterns. They might not be large enough to fill 20 m of pond bottom up! As already addressed above, water depth varies much more in the youngest part of the quarry pond (the area north of PeGraWa) compared to the southern part. The rather smooth pond bottom in the south could therefore indeed be caused by long lasting sedimentation processes e.g. from the gravel washing or during flooding events of the nearby Leine.

Especially in some parts at the north of the lake where excavation is still ongoing, we measured slopes of up to 70° at some locations, i.e. an increase in pond depth of ~3 m with 1 m horizontal distance to the shore. As long as the shore walls are stable, steepness alone is of course no problem for experienced swimmers. Inexperienced swimmers, on the other hand, can drown in much shallower waters that have less steep shores. A slope map derived from the bathymetric map, however, shows only a maximum slope of ~23° (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Map of slopes (°) derived from the bathymetric map of the Rosdorfer Baggersee.

The steepest slopes are found in a very narrow strip along the northeast shore of the Rosdorf quarry pond and on the shore opposite the PeGraWa. There are also steeper slopes off the shores of the

southern testicle of PeGraWa, but they are in much deeper waters farther from shore, so they are not a hazard to recreationalists. The map clearly lacks the few extreme drops due to the 2x2 m resolution, their rare occurrence, and the fact that interpolation techniques usually tend to flatten out extreme values. We attempted to address this deficiency by using a nugget of zero in the variogram. The zero nugget forces the interpolated map to exactly match the measured depths at each measurement location, thus precisely illustrating the few exceptionally steep slopes. However, a zero nugget model did not converge. Using a very small nugget (0.01) resulted in an extremely variable map with many abrupt jumps, even in the old area of the pond. We attribute this to not inconsiderable measurement errors in our data. Thus, more smoothing of the data is probably more realistic. Based on this consideration, we ultimately decided against changing the original nugget from Figure 3 and accept the fact that the few extremely steep spots cannot be adequately mapped this way.

Readers should keep in mind that the authors did not design their samples to be representative of the slope values. To do so, more points would have had to be specifically collected at varying distances from shore. Therefore, the slope map we present should be considered only as a byproduct of our work. Nevertheless, this map can (in addition to the bathymetric map) still help avoiding accidents: Activities such as cooling down feet during hiking trips at hot summer days and walking dogs should be conducted at shallower shores. In-water activities like soaking, swimming, dipping, snorkeling, diving, splashing and boating should take place at a safe distance from shores where slopes are steep.

Unquestionably the bathymetric map presented here was created with very simple means. The accuracy of the GPS can vary up to 5 m. However, this deviation does not affect the maximum depth of the quarry pond, which was even confirmed by the brick and tape measure method. We also cross-checked our data from the expedition on foot with Google Earth images of the shoreline (especially in areas where the shoreline is extremely steep and therefore little affected by the annual fluctuations in the quarry pond level). Here, most of our sample points matched the shoreline on the Google Earth images very well. Still, the kriging procedure might cause some error especially in the north and mostly directly at the shores, as 10 fold cross validation revealed. However, these inaccuracies are somewhat averaged out in the map with the 2x2 m resolution. Certainly, the slope map derived from the bathymetric map underestimates the slopes at the few very steep locations.

We also think that the density of the points is so high, that it is very unlikely that we missed “the one spot” where the quarry pond is as deep as 40 m or even 60 m. Readers should also consider, that another unnamed person already took many readings with the echo-sounder to determine spatial variability of quarry pond depth and to get an estimate of the approximate location of the deepest spot even before the first full scale expeditions. Here, no other deep holes in the quarry pond bottom were found. Further, the echo sounder could also have produced erroneous measurements, particularly if the device is not held exactly orthogonal to the water surface. In this case the corresponding distance to the quarry pond bottom would even be longer. Since a maximum depth of 23 m was measured, it could be that the quarry pond is even shallower than shown on our map.

Conclusion and Outlook

The Rosdorfer Baggersee is found to be not deeper than 23 m and so all sources on maximum depth of the quarry pond are most likely wrong. Although our approach is very simple and certainly many inaccuracies remain, our map is likely a much better source for the maximum depth of the Rosdorfer Baggersee than to just rely on unverified public claims on its maximum depth. Some sections of the pond's shoreline have extremely steep slopes and should not be walked on, as loose gravel can slide off and pose a hazard to recreationists. Our bathymetric map may be refined in future studies, especially close to the shore, where the steep edges may require a higher sampling intensity to assess the fine-scale changes in pond depth.

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Author contributions

All authors contributed to the concept, design, data analyses and writing. None of the authors admits to having been involved in the measurements.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests. No animals were harmed in writing this study.

Date and code availability statement

The GPS and echo sounder measurements are available at doi: [10.5281/zenodo.7050421](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7050421). The script for generating the bathymetric map can be downloaded from doi: [10.5281/zenodo.7050440](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7050440)